

DEVELOPMENT OF A REAL-TIME AGRICULTURAL MONITORING SYSTEM USING LORA COMMUNICATION

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Abstract - This paper presents the development of a remote monitoring system using the Heltec ESP32 Wi-Fi LoRa V3. The system collects soil moisture, temperature and air humidity data through DHT11 and YL-100 resistive soil sensors, transmitting them via LoRa network. The receiving hardware displays the data on an OLED display and on an HTML page accessible via local Wi-Fi. The system, designed for agricultural applications, aims at long-distance communication with low power consumption, functional and applicable to the agricultural sector.

Keywords: LoRa, Monitoring, Agriculture, Heltec ESP32 WiFi LoRa.

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture is one of the oldest and most essential activities of humanity, being fundamental for the production of food and raw materials that sustain societies around the world. With population growth and increasing demand for food, improving the efficiency of agricultural practices is essential. This includes the intelligent use of natural resources, such as water and soil, and the adoption of new technologies is necessary to optimize crop management and increase productivity, especially in rural and remote areas with limited infrastructure [1].

In modern agriculture, monitoring environmental data, such as temperature, air humidity and soil moisture, plays an important role. Continuous monitoring of these variables allows farmers to make informed decisions about irrigation, planting and harvesting, which results in better resource management and higher crop yields. In addition, the ability to collect and analyze this data in real time can help prevent waste and mitigate negative impacts, such as soil degradation and excessive water use [1].

In this scenario, long-range and low-power communication technologies, such as LoRa (Long Range), emerge as promising solutions for the remote monitoring of large agricultural areas. LoRa technology is ideal for transmitting small data packets over long distances, making it perfect for collecting environmental information in regions with poor internet and power coverage. These characteristics make LoRa a viable option for both small and large rural producers, especially where access to more advanced technologies is limited [2][3].

This work describes the development of a remote monitoring system using LoRa technology, implemented with the Heltec ESP32 Wi-Fi LoRa V3. The system was designed to collect soil moisture, temperature and air humidity data, using the YL-100 sensor and the DHT11. This data is transmitted via LoRa to a second device, which displays the information on an OLED display and makes it available on a Wi-Fi-accessible HTML page. Although tested in a laboratory environment, the system is designed to operate on large agricultural sites, offering a low-cost and energy-efficient solution for real-time monitoring of environmental data.

DEVELOPMENT

The system was developed to operate in agricultural environments, where collecting data such

as temperature, air humidity and soil moisture is crucial for decision-making today. The choice of sensors, although based on their availability, proved to be adequate for the testing objectives. The DHT11 sensor was used to monitor air temperature and humidity, while a YL-100 resistive soil sensor was used to measure soil moisture. Although these are low-cost sensors with limited accuracy, they sufficiently demonstrated the system's functionality, particularly for less complex agricultural applications. Figure 1 shows how the components were connected to the transmitting device. The receiving device only has a LoRa antenna attached, as it simply displays the received information.

Figure 1 - Electrical diagram.

The integration of the OLED display into the receiver hardware was configured to ensure a clear display of the received data. With each new transmission, the display showed the ID of the device transmitting the readings, followed by the temperature, humidity and soil moisture information. The device's IP was also displayed, allowing remote access to the HTML page, requiring only to be connected to the same WiFi network in which the receiver was configured in the programming. In addition, the display showed the date and time of the last update and the RSSI value, indicating the loss of the received LoRa signal. This organized layout facilitated the practical use of the system in the field, offering a clear and immediate visualization of the data.

Configuring the LoRa network was a critical step, requiring adjustments to ensure stable and efficient communication between the devices. The project used the 915 MHz band, with transmission power adjusted to 21 dBm, minimizing signal loss. Although few changes were made to the initial configurations, the

power was increased to ensure greater reliability in short-distance tests. The structure of the transmitted message consists of information such as the device ID, temperature, humidity, and soil moisture status. The message has been formatted in a standardized way to facilitate decoding at the receiver and is formatted as: “readingID/temperature&humidity#soil”. Minor adjustments have been made to the decimal places of the temperature and humidity data without compromising clarity or performance.[4]

In the development of the embedded code, data transmission and reception were implemented to ensure efficient separation of information. In the transmitter, the data was formatted in a single string, containing all the information as previously mentioned. In the receiver, this string is received and properly separated into its corresponding variables, allowing each piece of data to be processed individually. The structure of the data separation logic is based on specific delimiters for each variable, thus ensuring the correct updating of the information on the display.

The implementation of the HTML page was integrated into the receiver system, using a pre-existing template adapted to the characteristics and needs of data visualization. With each new data collection, the page is reloaded with the most recent information, allowing the data to be viewed remotely by any device connected to the same Wi-Fi network. This simplified the development of the web interface, focusing on the functionality of the system.[4]

Although the system was powered by a USB port during testing, the Heltec ESP32 was designed to run on batteries, and this functionality was considered for the future. The device has the ability to send battery percentage, for example, which would be important for field applications. However, this function was not tested at this early stage, as the focus was on validating the overall functionality of the system. The device's low power consumption makes it ideal for long-term applications in agricultural areas with limited infrastructure.

The code for the transmitter and receiver devices was structured in the Arduino IDE into different functions (voids), each responsible for a specific task, such as reading sensors, transmitting via LoRa, displaying on the OLED and sending data to the HTML page. This modular approach facilitated debugging and troubleshooting, allowing for quick and accurate adjustments. Thus, the development of the embedded system and updates with new functionalities became easier, as there is a lot of literature regarding problem situations and the solution, which involves small adjustments to the code.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The tests performed with the developed monitoring system shown in Figure 2 revealed interesting behaviors, both in terms of functionality and device performance. Communication between the transmitting and receiving hardware worked as expected, though there were variations in the update time. In some cases, updates were fast, while in others there was a longer delay, which can be attributed to variability in data transmission over the LoRa network, but nothing that compromised the

functionality of the system. This type of variation is common in low-power, long-range networks, especially in closed environments or with obstacles that can interfere with signal quality.

Figure 2 – Design of the transmitter device physically assembled and in the real application testing phase

One challenge observed during testing was the instability in the receiver's connection to the Wi-Fi network. The receiver hardware, which uses the Heltec ESP32 Wi-Fi LoRa V3, had difficulty connecting to the Wi-Fi, requiring several resets before establishing the connection. At times, the connection was fast and at other times the connection was difficult due to instability in the module's components, or even due to the quality of the Wi-Fi signal in the test environment. This may be a limitation of the module itself, which occasionally has difficulty locating available Wi-Fi networks. Once connected, the system worked without problems, updating the information on both the OLED display and the HTML page as designed. To place the project in real environments, it is necessary to evaluate the quality of the module's components, sensor characteristics and the stability of the Wi-Fi signal, especially in situations where connectivity needs to be immediate. Regarding the communication range via LoRa, the tests were performed at a distance of approximately 20 meters, significantly less than the long-range potential that LoRa technology can provide. Even at short distances, there was a small amount of packet loss, which is to be expected due to the controlled environment and the limitations of the antenna used. A more suitable antenna could reduce packet loss, increasing communication efficiency. However, the system was able to maintain the connection, and the information was updated correctly on the OLED screen and HTML page, indicating that basic operation was correct.

The results of the measurements, both for temperature, humidity, and soil moisture, were displayed correctly on the device's OLED display and on the HTML page. The data on the OLED was updated whenever a new data packet was received, following the standardization of the message format implemented in the code. The display layout was designed to be clear and functional, showing the main information, the IP address for accessing the HTML page, and the RSSI value (indicator of the received

signal strength), in addition to the time and date of the last update, as shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4 below.

Figure 3- Receiving the data in HTML page.

Figure 4 - Receiver device receiving data

The LoRa network performance was satisfactory, with normal variations in the RSSI value due to distance and obstacles in the environment. Even so, communication between the transmitter and receiver remained stable during the tests, without major interruptions or failures that compromised functionality. These observations reinforce the suitability of using LoRa in agricultural monitoring applications, where long distances and low power consumption are essential.

Regarding scalability, the system demonstrated the potential to support various types of sensors, making it adaptable to various applications. The simplicity of programming facilitates the inclusion of new sensors or even multiple devices, which opens space for future expansions of the project. A significant improvement will be the inclusion of a data logging system to create a history of measurements, allowing for more detailed monitoring of the monitored environmental conditions.

In summary, the test results met and in some cases exceeded initial expectations. From the tests carried out in a laboratory environment, it was possible to observe possibilities for improvement, such as the integration of an independent energy source (solar panel), the inclusion of more sensors, long-range tests in open fields, encryption for the message and monitoring of data from any place with Internet access, not just on the local network, making it an IoT (Internet of Things) device. These improvements will be essential for the scalability of the project, making it

more robust and with applications in a real agricultural monitoring area.

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